

Postpartum Blues and Other Predictors of Postnatal Depression: A Rural Tertiary Care Hospital-Based StudyAmithab M. Nambiar¹, Yashas B. P.², Keerthi Sundar G. S.³, Vinay H. R.⁴¹Junior Resident, Dept. of Psychiatry, Adichunchanagiri Institute of Medical Sciences, Karnataka, India²Undergraduate Student, Adichunchanagiri Institute of Medical Sciences, Karnataka, India³Assistant Professor, Dept. of Psychiatry, Siddaganga Medical College and Research Institute, Tumakuru, Karnataka, India,⁴Associate Professor, Dept. of Psychiatry, Adichunchanagiri Institute of Medical Sciences, Karnataka, India

Received: 01-03-2025 / Revised: 15-04-2025 / Accepted: 21-05-2025

Corresponding author: Dr. Keerthi Sundar G. S.

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Background:** Mood-related disorders such as postpartum blues and postnatal depression frequently affect women following childbirth, particularly in rural settings. These disorders, if left unrecognized, can adversely impact maternal wellbeing and infant care.**Objectives:** (1) To assess the incidence of postpartum blues and postnatal depression. (2) To determine the association between postpartum blues and postnatal depression. (3) To evaluate the predictive value of obstetric and psychosocial factors in postnatal depression.**Methods:** This prospective observational study included 53 postpartum women attending a rural tertiary care center. Participants were evaluated using Stein's Maternity Blues Scale within the first week postpartum and the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) at one and two months. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS.**Results:** Postnatal depression (EPDS ≥ 10) was found in 26.4% of participants. Although postpartum blues was prevalent (60.3%), its association with depression was not statistically significant. Similarly, no single obstetric or psychosocial factor emerged as a strong predictor, although previous abortion and gestational age showed weak trends.**Conclusion:** A notable proportion of rural women experience depressive symptoms after childbirth. These findings support the routine screening for postpartum depression, independent of risk factors.**Keywords:** Postpartum depression, EPDS, Stein's Scale, rural psychiatry, obstetric predictors.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Postpartum mental health concerns, particularly postpartum blues and postnatal depression, are increasingly recognized as significant public health issues. While postpartum blues is considered a transient and relatively mild emotional disturbance, postnatal depression may be more persistent and has the potential to impact not only maternal wellbeing but also the developmental outcomes of the child. [18-25]

The estimated global prevalence of postnatal depression ranges from 10% to 20%, with some studies in low-resource settings reporting even higher rates. [20] In India, recent meta-analyses suggest a pooled prevalence of around 22%, with women in rural areas facing greater vulnerability due to socioeconomic stress, limited mental health awareness, and poor access to services. [7,25]

Although postpartum blues is highly prevalent, affecting up to 85% of new mothers, its role as a potential early indicator for more severe postpartum depression is still under investigation. [3,19,23] Various clinical and psychosocial risk factors, including mode of delivery, previous pregnancy complications, family structure, and social support, may contribute to vulnerability for depression. [9-11,24]

Despite the significant impact of these conditions, screening and early detection efforts remain insufficient in many rural Indian settings. This study aims to assess the incidence of postpartum blues and depression and explore the relationship between commonly reported obstetric and psychosocial factors with depressive outcomes in a rural tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods

A prospective observational study was conducted at a rural tertiary care hospital over six months. The study involved 53 postpartum women who delivered live-born infants. Inclusion criteria were age ≥ 18 years, uncomplicated delivery, and willingness to participate.

Exclusion criteria included stillbirths, congenital anomalies, pre-existing psychiatric illness, or refusal to consent.

Data were collected using a structured proforma documenting sociodemographic and obstetric factors. The Stein's Maternity Blues Scale [13] was administered within the first postpartum week. The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) [14] was used at one and two months postpartum. A score of ≥ 10 on EPDS indicated probable depression.

Follow-up assessments were conducted via telephone. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS v22. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression were applied as appropriate. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Of the 53 women included, the mean age was 23.7 years (SD = 3.46). Most participants belonged to below poverty line (BPL) households. 33 had vaginal deliveries and 20 underwent cesarean sections. Thirteen had a history of abortion. Postpartum blues was seen in 60.3%, while 26.4% screened positive for postnatal depression. Postpartum blues and depression were not significantly associated ($p = 0.227$). Prior abortion showed a weak trend ($p = 0.175$), and gestational age was not significantly linked to depressive symptoms ($p = 0.384$).

Discussion

This study found that 26.4% of rural postpartum women exhibited depressive symptoms. This aligns with national data from similar populations. [7,9,25] Although postpartum blues was common, it was not a significant predictor of postnatal depression in our cohort.

This may reflect strong social support structures or individual resilience. Other variables like mode of delivery, analgesia, or abortion history showed non-significant associations. These findings support the importance of routine screening over selective screening based on risk profiles. EPDS remains a practical tool for early detection.

Conclusion

Postnatal depression is a significant concern in rural maternal health. While individual risk factors may not be reliable predictors, the overall prevalence

underscores the importance of routine mental health assessment. Integration of screening tools like EPDS into primary care is both feasible and beneficial.

Limitations

The study's main limitations were its small sample size, single-center design, and reliance on self-reported measures. Diagnostic interviews were not performed to confirm screening results. Findings may not generalize to urban populations or those with different cultural backgrounds.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Adichunchanagiri Institute of Medical Sciences. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality was maintained, and participants with high EPDS scores were referred for psychiatric evaluation.

References

1. Takahashi Y, Tamakoshi K. Factors associated with early postpartum maternity blues and depression tendency among Japanese mothers. *Nagoya J Med Sci.* 2014; 76:129–138.
2. Rai S, Pathak A, Sharma I. Postpartum psychiatric disorders: Early diagnosis and management. *Indian J Psychiatry.* 2015; 57(3):216–221.
3. Josefsson A, Berg G, Nordin C, Sydsjö G. Prevalence of depressive symptoms in late pregnancy and postpartum. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.* 2001; 80(3):251–255.
4. Sword W, Busser D, Ganann R, McMillan T, Swinton M. Women's care-seeking experiences after postpartum depression. *BJOG.* 2011; 118(8):966–977.
5. Chaaya M, Campbell OMR, El Kak F, Shaar D, Harb H, Kaddour A. Postpartum depression: prevalence and determinants in Lebanon. *Arch Womens Ment Health.* 2002; 5(2):65–72.
6. Breese McCoy SJ, Beal JM, Saunders B, Hill EN. Risk factors for postpartum depression: A retrospective investigation. *J Reprod Med.* 2008; 53(3):166–170.
7. Upadhyay RP, Chowdhury R, Salehi A, Sarkar K, Singh SK, Sinha B, et al. Postpartum depression in India: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2017; 95(10):706–717C.
8. Gupta S, Mehrotra S, Arora S, Sethi S, Bala R. Postpartum depression in North Indian women: Prevalence and risk factors. *J Obstet Gynaecol India.* 2013; 63(4):223–229.
9. Dadhwal V, Sagar R, Bhattacharya D, Kant S, Misra P, Choudhary V, et al. Prevalence of postpartum depression & anxiety among women in rural India: Risk factors & psychosocial correlates. *Indian J Med Res.* 2023; 158(4):407–416.

10. Sheela CN, Venkatesh S. Screening for postnatal depression in a tertiary care hospital. *J Obstet Gynaecol India*. 2016; 66(S1):S72–S76.
11. Kumar R. Postnatal mental illness: A transcultural perspective. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol*. 1994; 29(6):250–264.
12. World Medical Association. Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects. *JAMA*. 2013; 310(20):2191–2194.
13. Stein G. The pattern of mental change and body weight change in the first post-partum week. *J Psychosom Res*. 1980; 24(3):165–171.
14. Cox JL, Holden JM, and Sagovsky R. Detection of postnatal depression: Development of the 10-item Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale. *Br J Psychiatry*. 1987; 150:782–786.
15. Murray D, Cox JL. Screening for depression during pregnancy with the Edinburgh Depression scale (EPDS). *J Reprod Infant Psychol*. 1990; 8(2):99–107.
16. Balam K, Marwaha R. Postpartum Blues. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023.
17. Misra P, Upadhyay RP, Anand K. Maternal mental health in India during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Indian J Psychiatry*. 2020; 62(4):401–407.
18. O'Hara MW, McCabe JE. Postpartum depression: current status and future directions. *Annu Rev Clin Psychol*. 2013; 9:379–407.
19. Sharma V, Mazmanian D. Sleep loss and postpartum psychosis. *Bipolar Disord*. 2003; 5(2):98–105.
20. Halbreich U, Karkun S. Cross-cultural and social diversity of prevalence of postpartum depression and depressive symptoms. *J Affect Disord*. 2006; 91(2–3):97–111.
21. Murray L, Cooper PJ. Effects of postnatal depression on infant development. *Arch Dis Child*. 1997; 77(2):99–101.
22. Stewart DE, Vigod SN. Postpartum depression: pathophysiology, treatment, and emerging therapeutics. *Annu Rev Med*. 2019; 70:183–196.
23. Hendrick V, Altshuler LL, Suri R. Hormonal changes in the postpartum and implications for postpartum depression. *Psychosomatics*. 1998; 39(2):93–101.
24. Wisner KL, Sit DK, McShea MC, et al. Onset timing, thoughts of self-harm, and diagnoses in postpartum women with screen-positive depression findings. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 2013; 70(5):490–498.
25. Patel V, Saxena S, Lund C, et al. Addressing the burden of mental, neurological, and substance use disorders: key messages from Disease Control Priorities. *Lancet*. 2016; 387(10028):1672–1685.